

Subject 1: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis on Risk Factors for Sporadic Food-Borne Illnesses

Part IX: Cryptosporidiosis

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The quality assessment stage was passed by 57 primary studies investigating risk factors for sporadic infection with *Cryptosporidium* spp., which were conducted between 1983 and 2015. From these, twenty-seven studies investigated exposures in children/infants, twenty-four in the mixed population, while nine studies focused on the susceptible population (predominantly immunodeficient people). These primary studies provided 568 ORs categorised for meta-analysis, being 70% of the meta-analytical data produced by observational studies from USA (136 ORs), UK (79 ORs), Australia (66 ORs), the Netherlands (66 ORs) and Canada (47 ORs). Forty-four studies (~77%) employed an unmatched experimental design and produced a total of 394 ORs. From these, 244 reported or computed ORs were not adjusted by any confounder (i.e., crude ORs), while the others were adjusted by using either unconditional logistic regressions (148 ORs) or Mantel-Haenzel method (2 ORs). On the other hand, thirteen studies (~23%) employed a matched experimental design, providing for meta-analysis a total of 174 ORs. Most of them were estimated by conditional logistic regressions (134 ORs). After methodological quality assessment, six primary studies were marked as being possibly affected by selection bias, which yielded a total of 84 potentially-biased ORs. With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations focused more on the multiple pathways of transmission (494 ORs) than on host specific factors (51 ORs) or travel (23 ORs).

According to this meta-analysis, the top four risk factors for acquiring cryptosporidiosis were person-to-person transmission (overall OR=5.65; 95% CI: 2.66 – 12.00 in children; overall OR=3.30; 95% CI: 2.72 – 3.99 in the mixed population; overall OR=2.61; 95% CI: 1.71 – 3.99 in the susceptible population), international travel (overall OR=3.03; 95% CI: 1.83 – 5.03 in the mixed population), suffering from an immunocompromising disease (overall OR=4.31; 95% CI: 2.60 – 7.16 in the mixed population; overall OR=2.25; 95% CI: 1.02 – 4.97 in children) or any other medical condition (overall OR=2.52; 95% CI: 1.20 – 5.29 in the mixed population; overall OR=1.85; 95% CI: 0.89 – 3.87 in the susceptible population).

In the mixed and children population, the global animal contact routes (overall OR=1.91; 95% CI: 1.51 – 2.42; and overall OR=1.88; 95% CI: 1.36 – 2.59, respectively) and the environmental-related pathways of transmission (overall OR=1.83; 95% CI: 1.50 – 2.23; and overall OR=1.49; 95% CI: 1.19 – 1.86, respectively) bore a discernably higher level of risk than the consumption of foods, as a whole (overall OR=1.38; 95% CI: 1.06 – 1.80; and overall OR=1.28; 95% CI: 1.00 – 1.65, respectively). By contrast, in the susceptible population, the global animal routes were not an important source of cryptosporidiosis (overall OR=0.84; 95% CI: 0.64 – 1.12), although the environmental-related pathways (overall OR=1.26; 95% CI: 0.95 – 1.67) still posed a higher level of risk than food consumption (overall OR=0.87; 95% CI: 0.55 – 1.37), as occurred in the mixed and children population.

Routes of transmission that followed the top four risk factors in importance were: contact with farm animals (overall OR=2.30; 95% CI: 1.81 – 2.91 in the mixed population; and overall OR=1.97; 95% CI: 1.28 – 3.02 in children) and exposure to recreational water (overall OR=2.20; 95% CI: 1.74 – 2.78). In the mixed population, the risk factor of attending day care, having a child at day care or changing nappies (overall OR=1.63; 95% CI: 1.09 – 2.45), widely considered as an important source of contagion, was surpassed in relevance by the environmental/animal pathways of contact with waste (overall OR=1.94; 95% CI: 1.34 – 2.82), living on a farm (overall OR=1.93; 95% CI: 1.29 – 2.90), poor personal hygiene (overall OR=1.73; 95% CI: 1.29 – 2.34) and drinking water (overall OR=1.71; 95% CI: 1.36 – 2.15). In the children population, attending day care (overall OR=1.74; 95% CI: 1.03 – 2.94) was at least as important a determinant of cryptosporidiosis as living on a farm (overall OR=1.80; 95% CI: 1.19 – 2.72) or having contact with pets (overall OR=1.69; 95% CI: 1.30 – 2.21). While in the susceptible population drinking water (overall OR=1.43; 95% CI: 1.09 – 1.87) bore higher risk of disease than living on a farm (overall OR=1.24; 95% CI: 0.63 – 2.45), in the children population, drinking water presented a lower level of risk (overall OR=1.37; 95% CI: 1.09 – 1.71). Contrarily to the mixed population, contact with waste was a less important source of cryptosporidiosis in the susceptible population (overall OR=0.98; 95% CI: 0.79 – 1.22) and in children (overall OR=1.13; 95% CI: 0.93 – 1.39).

In the mixed population, consumption of some foods such as BBQ foods (overall OR=2.00; 95% CI: 1.62 – 2.48), other meats (overall OR=1.98; 95% CI: 1.26 – 3.11) and composite dishes eaten out (overall OR=1.72; 95% CI: 1.22 – 2.41) conveyed, on average, higher odds of acquiring cryptosporidiosis than the known day care/nappy changing pathway. Food vehicles found to pose a lower risk of transmission of cryptosporidiosis, although still significant, were: fruits (overall OR=1.63; 95% CI: 0.98 – 2.24), milk (overall OR=1.51; 95% CI: 1.07 – 2.01), cheese/dairy RTE foods (overall OR=1.31; 95% CI: 1.01 – 1.70) and bottled water/ice (overall OR=1.25; 95% CI: 0.91 – 1.72). Routes of exposures likely to be minor sources of cryptosporidiosis, or weakly associated with the disease, were: contact with pets (overall OR=1.48; 95% CI: 0.75 – 2.92), red meats (overall OR=1.08; 95% CI: 0.79 – 1.49), contact with garden and soil (overall OR=1.08; 95% CI: 0.71 – 1.64), composite RTE (overall OR=0.79; 95% CI: 0.55 – 1.13), vegetables (overall OR=0.74; 95% CI: 0.61 – 0.90) and domestic travel (overall OR=0.65; 95% CI: 0.33 – 1.29) in the mixed population. In the susceptible population, the least important or non-significant pathways of transmission of *Cryptosporidium* spp. were bottled water (overall OR=0.82; 95% CI: 0.47 – 1.42) and contact with pets (overall OR=0.78; 95% CI: 0.57 – 1.06). Breastfeeding could not be proven to exert a protective effect against cryptosporidiosis infection in infants (overall OR=0.94; 95% CI: 0.59 – 1.49).

Finally, the practice of not washing vegetables before consumption was found to be a significant risk factor on its own for acquiring cryptosporidiosis; since, on meta-analysis, people who ate fruits and vegetables and became ill with cryptosporidiosis were 1.57 times (95% CI: 1.02 – 2.42) more likely to have consumed it without previous washing than those who consumed the same type of food but did not acquire the disease.

3. Results

3.9 *Cryptosporidium*

3.9.1 *Descriptive statistics*

In the systematic review of risk factors for human infection with *Cryptosporidium* spp., a total of 1985 clean bibliographic sources were identified using appropriate keywords in five bibliographic search engines, from which 123 case-control and cohort studies passed the full assessment for eligibility (Figure 1). From these, sixty-six fully-documented case-control studies investigated the source(s) of outbreaks and were kept in the JabRef file as their data can be readily extracted. Meta-analysis was undertaken on data either extracted or calculated from 57 primary studies – cohort and case-control studies – focusing on sporadic disease (Figure 1). These published studies were conducted in years spanning from 1983 and 2015. Table 1 compiles a list of the primary studies along with their main features. The eligible studies jointly provided 568 odds-ratios categorised for meta-analysis. A total of 231 ORs were retrieved from 21 case-control studies performed before the year 2000, while 337 ORs were excerpted from 36 case-control studies performed after 2000. Meta-analytical data were obtained from primary studies conducted in 31 countries, although studies from only 5 countries generated ~70% of the ORs retrieved. These were: USA (136 ORs), UK (79 ORs), Australia (66 ORs), the Netherlands (66 ORs) and Canada (47 ORs) (Figure 2, top).

Primary studies investigated risk factors in different types of population, namely children (27 studies), mixed population (24 studies) and susceptible population, which included immunodeficient individuals (8 studies) and elderly population (1 study). Separate meta-analyses were then adjusted on the mixed population (382 ORs), children (117 ORs) and susceptible (69 ORs) (Figure 2, bottom left). Only when the observations within a data partition (i.e., subset for a risk factor or pathway) were too few, the meta-analysis model was fitted to the whole subset without distinction of population type. Only thirteen case-control studies employed a matched experimental design and produced a total of 174 categorised ORs, which represented 30% of the data. Of these, 46 ORs were computed in multivariate analysis whereas 128 were obtained in univariate analysis. ORs from matched designs were mostly estimated by conditional logistic regression (134), while only a few by Mantel-Haenzel (21) and the simple chi-square test (18). From the 44 studies that applied an unmatched design, a total of 394 ORs were extracted or calculated, which constituted 70% of the meta-analytical data. A total of 341 ORs were computed in univariate analysis while 53 in multivariate analysis. Most of the ORs from unmatched designs were estimated using chi-square (244) and UL (148) whilst only 2 ORs were MH-estimates adjusted by a confounding

variable. Bringing together the matched and unmatched designs, 379 ORs (67% of the data) were not adjusted by any confounder (crude ORs), while 189 ORs (33%) were adjusted using either MH or logistic regressions (Figure 3).

Figure 1. Flow chart of literature search for case-control or cohort studies of human cryptosporidiosis

*Records kept in JabRef with PDFs files annexed

Figure 2. Distribution of the number of odds-ratios (y-axis) extracted from case-control studies of sporadic cryptosporidiosis by country (top left), population type (bottom left) and pathway of exposure (bottom right)

Figure 3. Pie-diagrams of the number of odds-ratios extracted from case-control and cohort studies of sporadic cryptosporidiosis by design (top left), analysis type (top right), model type (middle left), odds-ratio type (middle right), study period cut off year 2000 (bottom left) and assigned potential for bias (bottom right)

Table 1. Characteristics of primary studies investigating risk factors for acquiring sporadic cryptosporidiosis included in the meta-analysis

StudyID	Country	Study period	Population	Design	Analysis & model	# ill/ non-ill	Quality # Final ORs/ Removed*
Abdel-Messih et al., 2005	Egypt	May 2000 - May 2002	Children	Unmatched	Uni -Chi Uni-UL	90 ill 791 non-ill	Good 2
Al-Dabbagh, 2010	Iraq	June 2003– Oct 2003	Children	Matched	Uni –Chi Multi-UL	100 ill 100 non-ill	Good 6
Al-Shibani et al., 2009	Egypt	2009	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	70 ill 222 non-ill	Good 1
Aragón et.al., 2003	USA	May 1996- Sep 1998	Susceptible	Matched	Uni –CL Multi-CL	49 ill 99 non-ill	Good 19/1
Bhattacharya et al., 1997	Bangladesh	1991-1994	Children	Unmatched	Uni –Chi Multi-UL	68 ill 204 non-ill	Good 2
Bouratbine et al., 1998	Tunisia	1997	Children	Unmatched	Uni –Chi	12 ill 120 non-ill	Good 1
Chacín-Bonilla et al., 2008	Venezuela	2017	Mixed	Unmatched	Multi-UL	67 ill 448 non-ill	Good 2
Chen et al., 2017	China	2011-2012	Children	Unmatched	Uni –Chi	40 ill 531 non-ill	Good 5
Cohen et al., 2008	USA	1992-2002	Children Adult Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	Not stated	Good 10
Cruz et al., 1988	Guatemala	July 1985- June 1986	Children	Unmatched	Uni –Chi	19 ill 110 non-ill	Good 1
Egger et al., 1990	Switzerland	June-Sep 1988	Children	Matched	Uni- Chi	19 ill 38 non-ill	Good 9
El-Shabrawi et al., 2015	Egypt	Sep 2007- Sep 2009	Children	Matched	Uni- Chi	14 ill 236 non-ill	Good 2
Firdu et al., 2014	Ethiopia	Feb-Aug 2011	Children	Unmatched	Uni –Chi	11 ill 18 non-ill	Poor 9/1
Fournet et al., 2013	Netherlands	Aug 2012	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	82 ill 125 non-ill	Good 5
Gallaher et al., 1989	Mexico	July-Oct 1986	Mixed	Matched	Uni-MH	24 ill 46 non-ill	Good 3
Giroto et al., 2013	Brazil	Dec 2009- Oct 2010	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni –Chi	3 ill 290 non-ill	Good 2
Glaser et al., 1998	USA	Apr 1992- Nov 1994	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni –Chi	48 ill 99 non-ill	Good 13/1
Goh et al., 2004	UK	Jan 1998-Feb 2000	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	152 ill 466 non-ill	Good 48
Hellard et al., 2003	Australia	Oct 1998- Aug 2000	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni –Chi	10 ill 24 non-ill	Good 10
Helmy et al., 2015	Egypt	Apr-June 2011	Children	Unmatched	Uni –Chi	81 ill 84 non-ill	Good 4
Hunter et al., 2004	UK	Feb 2001- May 2002	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	427 ill 400 non-ill 261 ill 351 non-ill	Good 29
Izadi et al., 2014	Iran	Sep 2009- Mar 2010	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	28 ill 394 non-ill	Good 3
Izadi et al., 2012	Iran	Nov 2008- Mar 2009	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	11 ill 172 non-ill	Good 7
Khalakdina et al., 2003	USA	July 1999- July 2001	Mixed	Matched	Uni-CL Multi-CL	26 ill 62 non-ill	Good 16/1

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Khan et al., 2004	Bangladesh	May 2001- Aug 2002	Children	Unmatched	Uni –Chi	46 ill 46 non-ill	Good 3
Kutima et al., 2015	Kenya	Jan 2011- June 2013	Children	Unmatched	Uni –Chi	36 ill 676 non-ill	Good 4
Lake et al., 2007	UK	2000-2004	Mixed	Matched	Multi –CL	3368 ill 3368 non-ill	Good 2
Mahdi and Ali, 2002	Iraq	2002	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni –Chi	5 ill 230 non-ill	Good 1
Manabe et al., 1998	USA	July 1989- 1997	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni –Chi	68 ill 129 non-ill	Good 2
Marder, 2012	USA	2003-2010	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni –UL	6534 ill 30890 non-ill	Poor 18
Mbae et al., 2013	Kenya	Jan 2010- Dec 2011	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	187 ill 1925 non-ill	Good 2
Mitra et al., 2016	India	2016	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni –Chi	59 ill 233 non-ill	Good 1
Mølbak et al., 1994	Guinea- Bissau	1992	Children	Matched	Multi-CL	125 ill 125 non-ill	Good 4
Mooji et al., 2015	Netherlands	2013-2015	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	312 ill 587 non-ill	Good 61
Moore et al., 2016	Cambodia	Apr-June 2012	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	38 ill 460 non-ill	Good 15/2
Morse et al., 2008	Malawi	Jan 2001- Dec 2002	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	24 ill 72 non-ill	Good 6
Nassar et al., 2017	Nigeria	July-Dec 2014	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	88 ill 100 non-ill	Good 4
Nchito et al., 1998	Zambia	Nov 1995- Mar 1996	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Uni-MH	37 ill 179 non-ill	Good 2
Ng et al., 2012	Australia	July-Aug 2010	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	15 ill 48 non-ill	Good 2/2
Nimri and Hijazi, 1994	Jordan	July 1992- Sep 1993	Children	Matched	Uni-Chi	18 ill 18 non-ill	Good 1
Osman et al., 2016	Lebanon	Jan 2013	Children	Unmatched	Uni-UL	26 ill 223 non-ill	Good 5
Pereira et al., 2002	Brazil	Aug 1998- May 1999	Children	Unmatched	Uni-UL	64 ill 380 non-ill	Good 2
Pintar et al., 2009	Canada	Apr 2005- Dec 2007	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	36 ill 801 non-ill	Poor 18
Ravel et al., 2013	Canada	June 2005- May 2009	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	51 ill 54 non-ill	Poor 29/3
Redlinger et al., 2002	Mexico	Aug 1999- Mar 2000	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	298 ill 345 non-ill	Poor 2
Robertson et al., 2002	Australia	June 1998- May 2001	Children Mixed	Matched	Uni-CL Uni-CL Multi-CL	64 ill 262 non-ill 201 ill 795 non-ill	Good 54
Roy et al., 2004	USA	1999-2001	Mixed	Matched	Uni-MH Multi-CL	267 ill 464 non-ill 233 ill 467 non-ill	Good 30
Sarkar et al., 2014	India	2008-2013	Children	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	411 ill 180 non-ill 113 ill 51 non-ill	Good 14
Solorzano-Santos et al., 2000	Mexico	2000	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	10 ill 122 non-ill	Good 6
Sorvillo et al., 1994	USA	1983-1990	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-MH	125 ill 2354 non-ill	Good 1

Srisuphanunt et al., 2008	Thailand	2007	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	23 ill 120 non-ill	Good 14/1
Tellevik et al., 2015	Tanzania	Aug 2010- July 2011	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	23 ill 397 non-ill	Good 2
Tumwine et al., 2003	Uganda	Nov 1999- Jan 2001	Susceptible	Matched	Uni-Chi	488 ill 1291 non-ill	Good 1
Valderrama et al., 2009	USA	Aug-Sep 2007	Mixed	Matched	Uni-CL Multi-CL	47 ill 92 non-ill 45 ill 89 non-ill	Good 27
Velasco et al., 2011	Colombia	Feb-Apr 2009	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	38 ill 93 non-ill	Good 7
Wilson et al., 2008	NewZealand	2006	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	534 ill 5395 non-ill	Poor 8/1
Yang et al., 2017	China	Oct-Nov 2014	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	73 ill 543 non-ill 73 ill 542 non-ill	Good 11

(*) Number of ORs removed for having mean values below 0.5, except those belonging to breastfeeding

During methodological quality assessment, potential for selection bias status was assigned to six case-control studies since, in those, the controls were not healthy individuals but people affected by another enteric disease such as giardiasis (Firdu et al., 2014, Redlinger et al., 2002), salmonellosis (Marder, 2012), amoebiasis (Ravel et al., 2013), campylobacteriosis (Wilson et al., 2008), and a group of them (Pintar et al., 2009). As it is not clear whether these controls shared routes of exposure with the case patients, the ORs extracted from the aforementioned studies were marked as having potential for selection bias. These case-control studies provided 84 potentially-biased ORs whose influence on the meta-analysed OR estimates was appraised by means of the Cook's distance. With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations focused much more on the multiple pathways of transmission (494 ORs) than on host specific factors (51 ORs) or travel (23 ORs) (Figure 2, bottom left). General information on the distribution of the number of ORs available for meta-analysis is presented in Figure 3 by study design, type of analysis, model, type of odds-ratio, study period and potential for bias status.

3.9.2 *Meta-analysis for host-specific risk factors and travel-, environment-, animal-, food-related and person-to-person pathways of transmission*

The association measures of cryptosporidiosis with most of its potential risk factors and pathways of transmission have not changed significantly in recent years, as implied by the non-significant effect of study period on the pooled ORs. Study period was found to be influential only in the meta-analyses on travel (Table 2B) and the global environmental pathways (Table 5B) in the mixed population. Such meta-analyses suggested that, in earlier years, international travel was a stronger determinant of disease (by ~ 1.6 times = $\exp(0.850)$ in Table 5B) than in recent years; whereas the set of environmental pathways became a stronger determinant of cryptosporidiosis in recent years, with an overall increase in odds by ~ 1.3 times ($1/\exp(-0.264)$ in Table 5B).

Table 2A. Meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for acquiring cryptosporidiosis by geographical region for the mixed (n=19 ORs) and susceptible (n=3 ORs) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.581	0.344	11	[-0.095 – 1.256]	0.092
Oceania	1.155	0.480	3	[0.212 – 2.098]	0.016
Europe	0.749	0.397	5	[-0.029 – 1.526]	0.059
Susceptible					
North America	-0.125	0.223	3	[-0.564 – 0.314]	0.577

Table 2B. Meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for acquiring cryptosporidiosis in the mixed (n=19 ORs) and the combined susceptible (n=3) and children (n=1) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	All Travel	0.637	0.316	19	[0.018 – 1.257]	0.044
(9 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Abroad	1.110 ^b	0.258	12	[0.603 – 1.616]	<.0001
	Any	-0.223 ^a	0.542	2	[-1.284 – 0.838]	0.680
	Inside	-0.428 ^a	0.349	5	[-1.113 – 0.256]	0.219
	Before 2000	0.850	0.366		[0.133 – 1.567]	0.020
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2833	QE(df=15)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3902	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	0.0001	0.0000			0.001
	Points removed	0				
Suscep	All Travel	0.348	0.509	4	[-0.651 – 1.347]	0.494
(2 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Abroad	0.709 ^b	0.368	2	[-0.013 – 1.432]	0.054
	Inside	-0.388 ^a	0.268	2	[-0.915 – 0.138]	0.147
	Before 2000*					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=2)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.4498	p=0.228		p=0.055	
	Publication bias	-0.0156	0.0110			0.157

Points removed 0

(*) All OR data were obtained in studies conducted before 2000

Figure 4. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of travel as a risk factor for cryptosporidiosis in the mixed (left) and susceptible (right) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 3A. Meta-analyses of host-specific factors for cryptosporidiosis by region for the mixed (n=13), children (n=9) and susceptible (n=6) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	1.357	0.383	4	[0.607 – 2.107]	<.0001
North America	1.276	0.306	3	[0.677 – 1.875]	<.0001
Oceania	2.235	0.541	2	[1.175 – 3.294]	<.0001
Europe	0.789	0.353	4	[0.098 – 1.479]	0.025
Children*					
Africa	1.050	0.111	5	[0.833 – 1.268]	<.0001
Asia	1.604	0.319	2	[0.979 – 2.229]	<.0001
North America	0.460	0.424	2	[-0.372 – 1.292]	0.278
Susceptible					
North America	0.516	0.380	4	[-0.229 – 1.262]	0.175
Asia/S.America	1.328	0.539	2	[0.272 – 2.385]	0.014

(*) Breastfeeding data are not considered in these calculations

Table 3B. Meta-analysis of host specific factors for cryptosporidiosis in the mixed (n=13), children (n=27) and susceptible population (n=6)

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (7 stud)	All host-specific	1.346	0.230	13	[0.895 – 1.797]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Immuno	1.462 ^b	0.258	10	[0.956 – 1.968]	<.0001
	Other med	0.924 ^a	0.378	3	[0.183 – 1.665]	0.015
	Before 2000					0.350
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2936	QE(df=11)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.9685	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	0.0016	0.0010			0.096
	Points removed	0				
Children (18 stud)	All host-specific*	1.073	0.101	9	[0.873 – 1.272]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Breastfed	-0.064 ^a	0.237	19	[-0.528 – 0.400]	0.787
	Chronic	1.584 ^c	0.770	2	[0.075 – 3.093]	0.040
	Immuno	0.813 ^b	0.403	7	[0.023 – 1.603]	0.043
	Before 2000					0.111
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.5548	QE(df=24)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	1.4438	p<.0001		p=0.059	
	Publication bias	0.0001	0.0005			0.767
Points removed	0					
Suscep (4 stud)	All host-specific	0.817	0.354	6	[0.122 – 1.511]	0.021
	Fixed effects					
	Immuno	1.117 ^b	0.531	2	[0.076 – 2.158]	0.035
	Other med	0.616 ^a	0.376	4	[-0.120 – 1.352]	0.101
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2224	QE(df=4)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.8100	p<.0001		p=0.028	
	Publication bias	-0.0092	0.0146			0.530
	Points removed	0				

(*) In the children population, the overall host-specific OR does not include breastfeeding

Figure 5. Funnel plot of the meta-analyses of host-specific risk factors for cryptosporidiosis in the mixed (top left), children (top right) and susceptible (bottom) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 3C. Meta-analysis on poor personal hygiene as risk factor for the transmission of cryptosporidiosis – Africa (2 ORs), Asia (1 OR) and West Europe (1 OR)

Exposure	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Poor personal hygiene (4 stud)	All data	0.552	0.153	4	[0.252 – 0.851]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Children	0.016 ^a	0.383	2	[-0.734 – 0.766]	0.966
	Mixed	0.654 ^b	0.167	2	[0.326 – 0.981]	<.0001
Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=2)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.0658	p=0.382		p=0.001	

Publication bias	-0.0009	0.0007	0.165
Points removed	0		

Table 4A. Meta-analyses of pathways related to animal contact for cryptosporidiosis by region in the mixed (n=70), children (n=29) and susceptible (n=14) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	1.103	0.360	7	[0.396 – 1.810]	0.002
North America	0.435	0.231	12	[-0.018 – 0.888]	0.060
North Europe	0.186	0.457	5	[-0.711 – 1.082]	0.685
Oceania	0.545	0.285	15	[-0.012 – 1.103]	0.055
West Europe	0.363	0.274	31	[-0.173 – 0.900]	0.184
Children					
Africa	0.929	0.225	9	[0.489 – 1.369]	<.0001
Asia	0.356	0.195	15	[-0.026 – 0.738]	0.067
West Europe	0.666	0.465	5	[-0.245 – 1.577]	0.152
Susceptible					
Asia	-0.274	0.419	3	[-1.096 – 0.548]	0.514
North Europe	-0.131	0.165	9	[-0.454 – 0.192]	0.427
South America	-0.302	0.396	2	[-1.077 – 0.474]	0.445

Table 4B. Meta-analyses of pathways related to animal contact for acquiring cryptosporidiosis in the mixed (n=70), children (n=30) and susceptible (n=14) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	All animal	0.649	0.121	70	[0.412 – 0.886]	<.0001
(15 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Farm	0.832 ^a	0.120	42	[0.596 – 1.068]	<.0001
	Occupational	0.450 ^a	0.283	4	[-0.103 – 1.042]	0.111
	Pets	0.390 ^a	0.347	24	[-0.291 – 1.070]	0.262
	Before 2000					0.981
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0402	QE(df=65)		QM(df=3)	

	s^2 (residual)	0.3720	$p < .0001$		$p = 0.480$	
	Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000			$< .0001$
	Points removed	2				
Children (12 stud)	All animal	0.632	0.163	30	[0.311 – 0.952]	$< .0001$
	Fixed effects					
	Farm	0.677 ^a	0.218	15	[0.250 – 1.105]	0.002
	Pets	0.527 ^a	0.136	15	[0.260 – 0.794]	$< .0001$
	Before 2000					0.311
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2923	QE(df=28)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.4585	$p = 0.001$		$p = 0.406$	
	Publication bias	-0.0019	0.0004			$< .0001$
	Points removed	0				
Suscep (6 stud)	All animal	-0.170	0.143	14	[-0.450 – 0.110]	0.235
	Fixed effects					
	Farm	0.216 ^a	0.347	3	[-0.464 – 0.897]	0.533
	Pets	-0.249 ^a	0.157	11	[-0.557 – 0.058]	0.113
	Before 2000					0.607
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=12)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.9857	$p = 0.418$		$p = 0.234$	
	Publication bias	0.0156	0.0100			0.120
	Points removed	0				

Figure 6. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of animal contact pathways as risk factors for cryptosporidiosis in the mixed (top left), children (top right) and susceptible (bottom) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 5A. Meta-analyses of environmental pathways for acquiring cryptosporidiosis by region in the mixed (n=155), children (n=36) and susceptible (n=31) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.546	0.119	72	[0.313 – 0.780]	<.0001
North Europe	0.215	0.208	12	[-0.193 – 0.623]	0.301
Oceania	0.830	0.205	26	[0.427 – 1.233]	<.0001
S.America/Asia	0.518	0.196	6	[0.133 – 0.903]	0.008
West Europe	0.414	0.183	39	[0.056 – 0.773]	0.023
Children					
Africa	0.524	0.146	13	[0.237 – 0.812]	0.001
Asia	0.188	0.077	16	[0.035 – 0.339]	0.016
Oceania	0.008	0.216	3	[-0.415 – 0.431]	0.970
South America	0.916	0.268	4	[0.389 – 1.442]	0.001
Susceptible					
Asia	0.336	0.308	9	[-0.268 – 0.940]	0.276
North America	0.157	0.172	18	[-0.180 – 0.495]	0.361
South America	0.391	0.364	4	[-0.322 – 1.104]	0.283

Table 5B. Meta-analyses of environmental pathways for acquiring cryptosporidiosis in the mixed (n=155), children (n=33) and susceptible (n=31) population – Oceania removed from the children population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z	
Mixed (20 stud)	All environment	0.606	0.100	155	[0.408 – 0.804]	<.0001	
	Fixed effects						
	Day care	0.491 ^b	0.207	10	[0.085 – 0.896]	0.018	
	Drink water	0.537 ^b	0.116	47	[0.309 – 0.764]	<.0001	
	Farm	0.658 ^c	0.207	18	[0.252 – 1.064]	0.002	
	Playground*	0.077 ^a	0.212	7	[-0.338 – 0.493]	0.716	
	Rec water	0.788 ^c	0.120	65	[0.552 – 1.024]	<.0001	
	Waste**	0.665 ^c	0.189	8	[0.296 – 1.035]	<.0001	
	Before 2000	-0.264	0.129		[-0.516 - -0.012]	0.040	
	Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1222	QE(df=148)		QM(df=6)		
	s^2 (residual)	0.3463	p<.0001		p<.0001		
	Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000			0.713	
	Points removed	0					
Children (13 stud)	All environment	0.398	0.114	33	[0.176 – 0.622]	0.001	
	Fixed effects						
	Day care	0.555 ^{bc}	0.268	3	[0.030 – 1.080]	0.038	
	Drink water	0.313 ^b	0.115	19	[0.088 – 0.538]	0.006	
	Farm	0.589 ^c	0.210	3	[0.177 – 1.000]	0.005	
	Rec water	1.414 ^d	0.488	2	[0.457 – 2.371]	0.004	
	Waste	0.124 ^a	0.103	6	[-0.077 – 0.326]	0.226	
	Before 2000					ND	
	Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0190	QE(df=28)		QM(df=5)		
	s^2 (residual)	0.4640	p=0.219		p<.0001		
	Publication bias	-0.0009	0.0005			0.079	
	Points removed	0					
	Suscep (7 stud)	All environment	0.232	0.144	31	[-0.051 – 0.515]	0.109
Fixed effects							
Day care		0.591 ^b	0.303	2	[-0.003 – 1.184]	0.051	
Drink water		0.355 ^a	0.137	18	[0.086 – 0.624]	0.010	
Farm		-0.330 ^a	0.491	2	[-1.293 – 0.633]	0.502	

Rec water	0.782 ^b	0.456	2	[-0.111 – 1.675]	0.086
Waste	-0.024 ^a	0.111	7	[-0.242 – 0.195]	0.833
Before 2000					0.639
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0201	QE(df=26)		QM(df=5)	
s^2 (residual)	0.5609	p=0.003		p=0.016	
Publication bias	-0.0004	0.0001			0.001
Points removed	0				

(*) Contact with garden and exposure to soil

(**) Contact with human faeces or lack of sanitation facilities

Figure 7. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of environmental pathways as risk factors for cryptosporidiosis in the mixed (top left), children (top right) and susceptible (bottom) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 6A. Meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of cryptosporidiosis by region in the combined mixed (n=65), children (n=6) and susceptible (n=7) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All					
Asia	0.731	0.204	6	[0.331 – 1.130]	<.0001
North America	0.955	0.039	23	[0.878 – 1.031]	<.0001
North Europe	0.888	0.096	7	[0.689 – 1.066]	<.0001
Oceania	0.988	0.054	23	[0.883 – 1.093]	<.0001
South America	0.906	0.314	4	[0.291 – 1.522]	0.004
West Europe	0.675	0.066	15	[0.546 – 0.804]	<.0001

Table 6B. Meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of cryptosporidiosis in the combined mixed (n=65), children (n=6) and susceptible (n=7) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All	Fixed effects					
(22 stud)	Children	1.732 ^b	0.384	6	[0.980 – 2.485]	<.0001
	Mixed	1.193 ^{ab}	0.098	65	[1.001 – 1.384]	<.0001
	Susceptible	0.960 ^a	0.216	7	[0.536 – 1.384]	<.0001
	Uni OR	-0.389	0.090		[-0.565 - -0.213]	<.0001
	Before 2000					0.848
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.3430	QE(df=74)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3878	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	0.0000	0.0000			0.048
	Points removed	0				

Figure 8. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of cryptosporidiosis in the combined mixed, children and susceptible population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 7A. Meta-analyses of food pathways for acquiring cryptosporidiosis by geographical region in the mixed (n=55), children (n=6) and susceptibility (n=5) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.148	0.121	25	[-0.089 – 0.386]	0.220
Oceania	0.208	0.275	3	[-0.331 – 0.748]	0.449
N-W Europe	0.292	0.122	27	[0.053 – 0.532]	0.017
Children					
Asia	0.181	0.166	6	[-0.144 – 0.507]	0.276
Susceptible					
Asia	-0.022	0.415	2	[-0.837 – 0.793]	0.957
North America	-0.199	0.280	3	[-0.749 – 0.350]	0.477

Table 7B. Meta-analyses of food pathways for acquiring cryptosporidiosis in the mixed (n=55), children (n=7) and susceptible (n=5) population – no geographical region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (11 stud)	All foods	0.323	0.136	55	[0.056 – 0.590]	0.018
	Fixed effects					
	Beverage*	0.224 ^b	0.162	10	[-0.094 – 0.542]	0.167
	Composite	0.511 ^b	0.159	19	[0.199 – 0.823]	0.001
	Dairy	0.471 ^b	0.220	10	[0.039 – 0.903]	0.032
	Meat	0.433 ^b	0.219	9	[0.003 – 0.863]	0.048
	Produce	-0.235 ^a	0.174	7	[-0.576 – 0.106]	0.177
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0794	QE(df=50)		QM(df=5)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.2548	p<.0001		p=0.001	
Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0003			0.790	
Points removed	0					
Children (4 stud)	All foods	0.250	0.130	7	[-0.005 – 0.505]	0.054
	Fixed effects					
	Composite	0.427 ^b	0.182	2	[0.069 – 0.784]	0.019
	Dairy	0.205 ^a	0.336	2	[-0.454 – 0.864]	0.542
	Produce	0.007 ^a	0.223	3	[-0.429 – 0.444]	0.974
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=4)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3039	p=0.199		p=0.119	
	Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0011			0.993
	Points removed	0				
Suscep (2 stud)	Water,meat,produce	-0.144	0.233	5	[-0.600 – 0.320]	0.536
	Fixed effects					
	Bottled water	-0.199	0.280	3	[-0.749 – 0.350]	0.477
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=2)			
	s^2 (residual)	0.0174	p=0.950			
	Publication bias					ND
	Points removed	0				

(*) Bottled water and ice

Figure 9. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of food pathways for acquiring cryptosporidiosis in the mixed (top left), children (top right) and susceptible (bottom) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 8A. Meta-analysis of meat consumption pathways for acquiring cryptosporidiosis by geographical region in the combined mixed (n=8) and susceptible (n=1) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.755	0.274	6	[0.217 – 1.292]	0.006
West Europe	0.188	0.157	3	[-0.119 – 0.496]	0.231

Table 8B. Meta-analysis of meat consumption pathways for acquiring cryptosporidiosis in combined mixed (n=9) and susceptible (n=1) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
(5 stud)	Red meats	0.082 ^b	0.163	3	[-0.236 – 0.401]	0.612
	Other meats	0.683 ^c	0.230	7	[0.233 – 1.134]	0.003
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=8)		QM(df=2)	
	s ² (residual)	0.2979	p=0.746		p=0.010	
	Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0005			0.665
	Points removed	0				

Figure 10. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of meat consumption pathways for acquiring cryptosporidiosis in the combined mixed and susceptible population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 9A. Meta-analysis of dairy consumption pathways for acquiring cryptosporidiosis by geographical region in the combined mixed (n=10) and children (n=2) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
West Europe	0.291	0.116	7	[0.063 – 0.519]	0.012
Other regions*	0.467	0.257	5	[-0.036 – 0.970]	0.069

(*) Asia (1 OR), North America (2 OR) and Oceania (2 OR)

Table 9B. Meta-analysis of dairy consumption pathways for acquiring cryptosporidiosis in the combined mixed (n=10) and children (n=2) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (6 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Cheese	0.269 ^a	0.133	4	[0.008 – 0.530]	0.044
	Milk	0.411 ^b	0.175	8	[0.069 – 0.754]	0.019
	Before 2000					0.278
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=10)		QM(df=2)	
	s ² (residual)	0.2046	p=0.574		p=0.008	
	Publication bias	-0.0004	0.0008			0.647
	Points removed	0				

Figure 11. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of dairy consumption pathways for acquiring cryptosporidiosis in the combined mixed and children (top right). Circle marker represents an OR measure with potential for bias

Table 10A. Meta-analysis of produce consumption pathways for acquiring cryptosporidiosis by geographical region in the combined mixed (n=7), children (n=3) and susceptible (n=1) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	-0.047	0.169	5	[-0.379 – 0.285]	0.780
Europe	-0.269	0.108	6	[-0.482 – -0.057]	0.013

Table 10B. Meta-analyses of produce consumption pathways for acquiring cryptosporidiosis in the combined mixed (n=7), children (n=3) and susceptible (n=1) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
(8 stud)	Fruits	0.488 ^b	0.261	3	[-0.024 – 0.806]	0.062
	Vegetables	-0.302 ^a	0.098	8	[-0.493 – -0.110]	0.002
	Before 2000					0.542
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=9)		QM(df=2)	
	s ² (residual)	0.1065	p=0.745		p=0.002	
	Publication bias	-0.0009	0.0009			0.300
	Points removed	0				

Figure 12. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of produce consumption pathways for acquiring cryptosporidiosis in the combined mixed, children and susceptible population

Table 11A. Meta-analysis of composite food consumption pathways for acquiring cryptosporidiosis by geographical region in the combined mixed (n=19) and children (n=2) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.047	0.020	13	[0.008 – 0.086]	0.017
West Europe	0.669	0.081	8	[0.510 – 0.828]	<.0001

Table 11B. Meta-analyses of composite food consumption pathways for acquiring cryptosporidiosis in the combined mixed (n=19) and children (n=2) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
(6 stud)	Dishes	0.541 ^a	0.174	17	[0.199 – 0.882]	0.002
	Fast-food	0.448 ^a	0.402	2	[-0.339 – 1.235]	0.265
	RTE	0.728 ^a	0.696	2	[-0.635 – 2.091]	0.295
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1423	QE(df=18)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3304	p<.0001		p=0.108	
	Publication bias	0.0009	0.0004			0.015
	Points removed	0				

Figure 13. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of composite food consumption pathways for acquiring cryptosporidiosis in the combined mixed and children population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

3.9.3 Meta-analysis on the risk of cryptosporidiosis due to consumption of RTE foods and BBQ foods

Table 12. Meta-analyses on the consumption of RTE (n=8) and BBQ (n=4) foods as vehicles for the transmission of cryptosporidiosis

Exposure	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
RTE foods (4 stud)	All RTE	0.065	0.193	8	[-0.314 – 0.443]	0.738
	Fixed effects					
	Composite RTE	-0.239 ^a	0.183	4	[-0.597 – 0.120]	0.193
	Dairy RTE	0.269 ^b	0.133	4	[0.008 – 0.530]	0.043
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=6)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.5922	p=0.608		p=0.056	
Publication bias	-0.0005	0.0018			0.771	
Points removed	0					
BBQ foods (2 stud)	All BBQ foods	0.695	0.107	4	[0.485 – 0.907]	<.0001
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=3)			
	s^2 (residual)	0.3153	p<.0001			
	Publication bias	-0.0006	0.0007			0.383
Points removed	0					

Figure 14. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses on the consumption of RTE (left) and BBQ (right) foods as vehicles for the transmission of cryptosporidiosis. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Figure 15. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on drinking water as a source of cryptosporidiosis in the distinct populations (n=84) ordered by country

Figure 16. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on the possible person-to-person pathways of transmission of cryptosporidiosis in the distinct populations (n=78) ordered by country

Figure 17. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on food as source of cryptosporidiosis in the distinct populations (n=68) ordered by food subcategory

The main results from the meta-analyses on risk factors and pathways of exposure were compiled by means of two forest plots: the first forest plot (Figure 18) was designed for comparing among the *global* risk categories as potential determinants of cryptosporidiosis in the mixed, susceptible and children population; and the other (Figure 19) for comparing among the *disaggregated* risk categories and specific pathways of exposure for the mixed population, children and susceptible population. To visually distinguish the most important routes of transmission, the pooled ORs listed in the forest plots were ranked by mean's decreasing order, and to assess the reliability in the pooled ORs, the number of ORs used in the computations were displayed.

Examining the global categories (Figure 18), the most important global risk factors for acquiring cryptosporidiosis were person-to-person contagion (overall OR=3.30; 95% CI: 2.72 – 3.99 in the mixed population; overall OR=5.65; 95% CI: 2.66 – 12.00 in children; and overall OR=2.61; 95% CI: 1.71 – 3.99 in the susceptible population); and the set of host-specific factors (overall OR=3.84; 95% CI: 2.45 – 6.03 in the mixed population; overall OR=2.92; 95% CI: 2.39 – 3.57 in children; and overall OR= 2.26; 95% CI: 1.12 – 4.53 in the susceptible population. Travel was at least the third most important source of cryptosporidiosis, at an overall OR of 1.89 (95% 1.02 – 3.51) in the mixed population and an overall OR of 1.41 (95% 1.02 – 3.51) in the susceptible population.

In the mixed and children population, the animal- (overall OR=1.91; 95% CI: 1.51 – 2.42; and overall OR=1.88; 95% CI: 1.36 – 2.59, respectively) and the environmental-related pathways of transmission (overall OR=1.83; 95% CI: 1.50 – 2.23; and overall OR=1.49; 95% CI: 1.19 – 1.86, respectively) bore a discernably higher level of risk than consumption of foods (overall OR=1.38; 95% CI: 1.06 – 1.80; and overall OR=1.28; 95% CI: 1.00 – 1.65, respectively). By contrast, in the susceptible population, the global animal routes, taken together, were not a significant source of cryptosporidiosis (overall OR=0.84; 95% CI: 0.64 – 1.12), although the environmental-related pathways (overall OR=1.26; 95% CI: 0.95 – 1.67) still posed a higher level of risk than food consumption (overall OR=0.87; 95% CI: 0.55 – 1.37), as observed in the mixed and children population.

It was found that keeping poor personal hygiene (overall OR=1.74; 95% CI: 1.29 – 2.34) could be a more important source of disease than consumption of foods. Within the broad food categories, the consumption of composite foods (overall OR=1.67; 95% CI: 1.22 – 2.28), dairy (overall OR=1.60; 95% CI: 1.04 – 2.47) and meat (overall OR=1.54; 95% CI: 1.00 – 2.37) posed higher odds of acquiring cryptosporidiosis than beverages, mostly comprising bottled water (overall OR=1.25; 95% CI: 0.91 – 1.72) and RTE foods (overall OR=1.06; 95% CI: 0.73 – 1.56). Produce was not a vehicle of transmission of cryptosporidiosis either in the mixed population (overall OR=0.79; 95% CI: 0.56 – 1.11) or in children (overall OR=1.01; 95% CI: 0.65 – 1.56).

Figure 18. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring cryptosporidiosis for global risk categories, ranked in decreasing order. The global risk categories presented are only those made up of at least n=3 ORs

Zooming into the disaggregated risk factors for cryptosporidiosis (Figure 19), it became evident that person-to-person transmission (overall OR=5.65; 95% CI: 2.66 – 12.00 in children; overall OR=3.30; 95% CI: 2.72 – 3.99 in the mixed population; overall OR=2.61; 95% CI: 1.71 – 3.99 in the susceptible population), international travel (overall OR=3.03; 95% CI: 1.83 – 5.03 in the mixed population), suffering from an immunocompromising disease (overall OR=4.31; 95% CI: 2.60 – 7.16 in the mixed population; overall OR=2.25; 95% CI: 1.02 – 4.97) or any other medical condition (overall OR=2.52; 95% CI: 1.20 – 5.29 in the mixed population; overall OR=1.85; 95% CI: 0.89 – 3.87 in the immunocompromised) were the top four risk factors for acquiring cryptosporidiosis. Routes of transmission that followed in importance were contact with farm animals (overall OR=2.30; 95% CI: 1.81 – 2.91 in the mixed population; and overall OR=1.97; 95% CI: 1.28 – 3.02 in children) and exposure to recreational water (overall OR=2.20; 95% CI: 1.74 – 2.78). In the mixed population, the risk factor of attending day care, having a child at day care or changing nappies (day care: overall OR=1.63; 95% CI: 1.09 – 2.45), widely considered as an important source of cryptosporidiosis, was surpassed in relevance by the environmental/animal pathways of contact with waste (overall OR=1.94; 95% CI: 1.34 – 2.82), living on a farm (overall OR=1.93; 95% CI: 1.29 – 2.90), poor personal hygiene (overall OR=1.73; 95% CI: 1.29 – 2.34) and drinking water (overall OR=1.71; 95% CI: 1.36 – 2.15). In the children population, attending day care (overall OR=1.74; 95% CI: 1.03 – 2.94) was at least as important a determinant of cryptosporidiosis as living on a farm (overall OR=1.80; 95% CI: 1.19 – 2.72) or having contact with pets (overall OR=1.69; 95% CI: 1.30 – 2.21). While in the susceptible population, drinking water (overall OR=1.43; 95% CI: 1.09 – 1.87) bore higher risk of disease than living on a farm (overall OR=1.24; 95% CI: 0.63 – 2.45), in the children population, drinking water (overall OR=1.37; 95% CI: 1.09 – 1.71) presented a lower level of risk. Contrarily to the mixed population, contact with waste was a less important pathway of transmission of cryptosporidiosis in the susceptible population (overall OR=0.98; 95% CI: 0.79 – 1.22) and in children (overall OR=1.13; 95% CI: 0.93 – 1.39).

In the mixed population, consumption of some foods such as BBQ foods (overall OR=2.00; 95% CI: 1.62 – 2.48), other meats (overall OR=1.98; 95% CI: 1.26 – 3.11) and composite dishes eaten out (overall OR=1.72; 95% CI: 1.22 – 2.41) were, on average, more important sources of cryptosporidiosis than the best known “day care/nappy changing” pathway. Food vehicles found to pose a lower risk of transmission of cryptosporidiosis, although still significant, were: fruits (overall OR=1.63; 95% CI: 0.98 – 2.24), milk (overall OR=1.51; 95% CI: 1.07 – 2.01), cheese/dairy RTE foods (overall OR=1.31; 95% CI: 1.01 – 1.70) and bottled water/ice (overall OR=1.25; 95% CI: 0.91 – 1.72).

Routes of exposures likely to be minor sources of cryptosporidiosis, or weakly associated with the disease, were: contact with pets (overall OR=1.48; 95% CI: 0.75 – 2.92), red meats (overall OR=1.08; 95% CI: 0.79 – 1.49), contact with garden and soil (overall OR=1.08; 95% CI: 0.71 – 1.64), composite RTE (overall OR=0.79; 95% CI: 0.55 – 1.13), vegetables (overall OR=0.74; 95% CI: 0.61 – 0.90) and domestic travel (overall OR=0.65; 95% CI: 0.33 – 1.29). In the susceptible population, the least important pathways of transmission of *Cryptosporidium* spp. were bottled water (overall OR=0.82; 95% CI: 0.47 – 1.42) and contact with pets (overall OR=0.78; 95% CI: 0.57 – 1.06). Breastfeeding could not be proven to exert a protective effect against cryptosporidiosis infection in infants (overall OR=0.94; 95% CI: 0.59 – 1.49).

Figure 19. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring cryptosporidiosis in the mixed, children and susceptible population for disaggregated risk categories, ranked in decreasing order. The disaggregated risk categories presented are only those made up of at least n=3 ORs

3.9.4 *Meta-analysis on the effect of handling food on the risk of transmission of cryptosporidiosis*

The only food data partitions comprising sufficient data that could support the assessment of the effect of handling (i.e., raw, undercooked and unwashed) were those of produce and dairy. Full estimates and funnel plots of the meta-analysis on the effects of handling are shown in the supplementary Tables S1 and S2, and Figures S1 and S2, respectively. For the cryptosporidiosis meta-analysis, no data partition had sufficient information on setting; thus, the effect of eating food prepared outside the home on the overall association with disease could not be appraised. However, since most of the data on composite foods – dishes – had the feature of having been prepared outside, the pooled OR estimate for dishes can be approximated to the setting “eating out”.

Table 13. Meta-analysed effects of handling on base ORs by relevant food class

Food class	Estimate	Mean	2.5 th percentile	97.5 th percentile
Fruits & vegg	OR(Base)	0.737	0.602	1.107
	OR(Unwashed)/OR(Base)	1.571	1.021	2.420
Milk & cheese	OR(Base)	1.439	1.084	1.909
	OR(Raw)/OR(Base)	1.130	0.681	1.878

On meta-analysis, people who ate fruits and vegetables and became ill with cryptosporidiosis were 1.571 times (95% CI: 1.021 – 2.420) more likely to have consumed it without previous washing than those who consumed the same type of food but did not acquire the disease (Table 13). Hence, the practice of not washing vegetables before consumption represents on its own a risk factor for cryptosporidiosis ($p=0.040$; Table S1). On the other hand, there was no evidence that consuming raw milk or raw milk cheese increased the risk of becoming infected cryptosporidiosis (OR(Raw)/OR(Base)=1.130; 95% CI: 0.681 – 1.878 in Table 13; $p=0.636$ in Table S2).

3.9.5 *Synthesis of the risks associated to preparation practices and poor handling of foods*

Most of the poor food handling habits explored in the primary studies related to hand hygiene before cooking and storage of food (Figure 20). Odds-ratios for infrequent handwashing as a potential determinant of cryptosporidiosis were significant in the susceptible population (ORs: 2.25-3.35) and children (ORs: 1.16 - 5.08). However, lack of hands hygiene could not be proven to be determinant of cryptosporidiosis in the mixed population (ORs: 0.92-0.97). Improper storage of food for later consumption could represent a risky practice when feeding children (ORs: 1.75 – 1.80).

Figure 20. Forest plot of the odds-ratios of acquiring cryptosporidiosis associated to poor food handling practices in the susceptible, mixed and children population

4 Conclusions

4.9 Meta-analysis on risk factors for sporadic cryptosporidiosis

- ❖ The outcomes from 57 case-control and cohort studies investigating host-specific factors and pathways of transmission for sporadic cryptosporidiosis were meta-analysed within appropriate data partitions, taking into account geographical region and period of study.
- ❖ The top three risk factors for acquiring cryptosporidiosis are person-to-person transmission (OR=5.65 in children; OR=3.30 in the mixed population; OR=2.61), international travel (OR=3.03 in the mixed population) and host-specific factors including immunocompromising disorders or other medical conditions (OR=3.84 in the mixed population OR=2.92 in children; and OR= 2.26 in the susceptible population).

- ❖ In the mixed and children population, the global animal contact routes (OR=1.91 and OR=1.88) and the environmental-related pathways of transmission (OR=1.83 and OR=1.49) pose a higher level of risk than the consumption of foods, as a whole (OR=1.38 and OR=1.28).
- ❖ By contrast, in the susceptible population, the global animal routes were not an important source of cryptosporidiosis (OR=0.84), although the environmental-related pathways (overall OR=1.26) still bore a higher level of risk than food consumption (OR=0.87).
- ❖ Routes of transmission that followed the top risk factors were: contact with farm animals (OR=2.30 in the mixed population; and OR=1.97 in children) and exposure to recreational water (OR=2.20).
- ❖ In the mixed population, the environmental/animal pathways of contact with waste (OR=1.94), living on a farm (OR=1.93), poor personal hygiene (OR=1.73) and drinking water (OR=1.71) turned out to be stronger determinants of disease than the best-known risk factor of attending day care, having a child at day care or changing nappies (OR=1.63)
- ❖ In children, attending day care (OR=1.74) was at least as important a source of cryptosporidiosis as living on a farm (OR=1.80) or having contact with pets (OR=1.69).
- ❖ Contrarily to the mixed population, contact with waste was a less important source of cryptosporidiosis in the susceptible population (OR=0.98) and in children (OR=1.13).
- ❖ In the mixed population, consumption of some foods such as BBQ foods (OR=2.00), other meats (OR=1.98) and composite dishes eaten out (OR=1.72) conveyed higher odds of acquiring cryptosporidiosis than the known day care/nappy changing pathway.
- ❖ Other foods with a lower, yet still significant, association with cryptosporidiosis in the mixed population were: fruits (OR=1.63), milk (OR=1.51), cheese/dairy RTE foods (OR=1.31) and bottled water/ice (OR=1.25).
- ❖ Minor or non-significant pathways of transmission of *Cryptosporidium* spp. in the mixed population were: contact with pets (OR=1.48), red meats (OR=1.08), contact with garden and soil (OR=1.08), composite RTE (OR=0.79), vegetables (OR=0.74) and domestic travel (OR=0.65; 95% CI: 0.33 – 1.29).
- ❖ In the susceptible population, non-significant pathways of transmission of *Cryptosporidium* spp. were bottled water (OR=0.82) and contact with pets (OR=0.78).
- ❖ Breastfeeding could not be proven to exert a protective effect against cryptosporidiosis infection in infants (OR=0.94).

- ❖ The practice of not washing raw vegetables before consumption was found to be a significant risk factor for acquiring cryptosporidiosis; increasing the odds of becoming ill by 1.57 times that of consuming washed raw vegetables.

5 References

5.9 Fifty-seven case-control and cohort primary studies assessing risk factors for cryptosporidiosis

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6 Supplementary tables and figures of the effects of handling on the transmission of cryptosporidiosis

Table S1. Meta-analysis of the effect of handling on the risk of cryptosporidiosis by consumption of fruits (n=3) and vegetables (n=8) in the combined mixed (n=7), children (n=3) and susceptible (n=1) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All	Base	-0.305	0.104	7	[-0.508 – -0.102]	0.003
(8 stud)	Unwashed	0.452	0.220	4	[0.021 – 0.884]	0.040
Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=9)			
	s^2 (residual)	0.1512	p=0.372			
	Publication bias	-0.0010	0.009			0.235
	Points removed	0				

Figure S1. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis on the effect of handling on the risk of cryptosporidiosis by consumption of fruits and vegetables

Table S2. Meta-analysis of the effect of handling on the risk of cryptosporidiosis by consumption of milk (n=8) and cheese (n=3) in the combined mixed (n=9) and children (n=2) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Both (6 stud)	Base	0.364	0.144	4	[0.081 – 0.647]	0.012
	Raw	0.122	0.259	7	[-0.384 – 0.630]	0.636
Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=9)			
	s^2 (residual)	0.1950	p=0.674			
	Publication bias	-0.0003	0.0008			0.689
	Points removed	0				

Figure S2. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis on the effect of handling on the risk of cryptosporidiosis by consumption of milk and cheese. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias